

Determination of Stormwater Drainage in University Campuses; Case Study of İzmir Katip Çelebi University Campus

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Abstract

Structural development grows rapidly with urbanization, resulting in more and more impervious areas and therefore stormwater cannot infiltrate underground. In recent years, stormwater management models have been developed to solve the problem. The models have been the subject of natural-based solutions for the last decade. The principle of stormwater management aims to control stormwater in urban areas. The systems aim to replace the traditional sewage system with blue-green infrastructure systems which consist of rainwater harvesting, rain gardens, vegetated swales, green roofs, green walls, permeable pavement, and rainwater tanks. The method transforms an impermeable surface of asphalt, brick, concrete, and stone into permeable design tools. Flooding, one of the main consequences of climate change, is the biggest challenge for cities. Therefore, areas with high building density need to be transformed and especially rainwater needs to be used efficiently. This study aims to develop a management model for the efficient use of stormwater in university campuses, which are an important spatial part of cities. In this context, firstly, areas with high drainage density were identified with the ArcGIS 10.4 program and then an effective drainage network was created within the campus using the Stormwater Management Model (SWMM). The campus-wide system can also be applied and easily adapted to the city. With this method, the ratio of permeable areas is increased and new design models are created in urban areas.

Keywords: Drainage density, Low Impact Development, SWMM, GIS

Introduction

The rate of urbanization has increased with population increases in cities and the natural land surface has turned into an artificial landscape surface due to expanding urban areas. As a result, the urban landscape texture has become an impermeable texture and rainwater cannot be infiltrated and the rate of surface runoff water has increased. Urban drainage systems are essential for urban areas. It is the most needed infrastructure element in the context of the interaction between human activities and the natural water cycle. There are two forms of drainage system. The first is the extraction of water for water supply and the second is the separation of the stormwater system from the regional natural drainage system (Emama, Edae, Fayisa, & Hirko, 2022). With urbanization, important problems and responsibilities have started to arise for city administrators and policymakers. Urban flooding is one of these problems. Urban floods occur due to reasons such as poor floodwater drainage systems, alteration of water catchment basins, and occupation of water bodies and low-slope areas (National Institute of Urban Affairs, 2016). Unplanned growth of urban areas has serious negative impacts on natural drainage surfaces. Short periods of heavy rainfall cause the risk of high flow floods (Rangari, Prashanth, Umamahesh, & Patel, 2018). Changes in precipitation patterns due to climate change and rapid urbanization have resulted in inadequate drainage systems and consequently led to flood risks in cities. In developing countries, especially urban floods pose serious risks and the traditional drainage networks used in cities do not meet the changing conditions due to climate change (Bibi, Reddythta, & Kebebew, 2023). The increase in population density with the beginning of migration from rural to urban areas has also changed land use. Land use changes also change flood flow characteristics. The increase in impervious surface elements in the urban landscape such as roads, parking lots, roof areas, etc. increases the volume of surface runoff and makes flooding more risky. Urbanization also reduces infiltration and decreases the rate of water entering the groundwater. Since the frequency of wind, which is among the climatic factors, has also been affected by climate change, the damage rate of floods has increased with

the effect of wind with heavy rainfall. In addition, the change in the vegetation cycle significantly affects the flow of water (Akhte, Hewa, Ahammed, Myers, & Argue, 2020).

Human history is changing due to various factors. Along with these changes, the cycle of water use is also changing. The sustainability rate of water resources in urban areas is seriously alarming. Therefore, there is a serious need for water management systems. With the impact of urbanization, the difference between the movement of water in permeable and impermeable areas is concretely noticeable. Impervious surfaces have a direct impact on the hydrological cycle (Saraswat, Kumar, & Mishra, 2016). The cycle of water in the natural and structured surface is highlighted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Hydrological Movement on urban and natural surfaces
(References: European Platform Urban Greening, 2021)

Most of the urban flood events are caused by very heavy rainfall. Flood risk is inevitable for a city, especially if these precipitation events occur at high rates in a short period of time. Flood hazard jeopardizes the safety of life and property and causes deep problems for the society (Axelsdottir, 2022). Therefore, there is a need to move from traditional floodwater management systems to modern management systems. While traditional systems focus on separating the floodwater line from the

waterbody, modern systems also focus on water quality. They focus on increasing biodiversity and reducing water pollution through quantitative and qualitative methods (Jotte, Raspati, & Azrague, 2017). The floodwater drainage system is a key component of floodwater management. Various drainage activities contribute to risk reduction. Floodwater management offers structural and operational practices with qualitative and quantitative uses. In urban environments, integrated water management is a crucial issue. Various types of flooding occur in urban environments. These include pluvial floods, flash floods, coastal floods, river floods, and catastrophic floods. There are both structural and non-structural interventions in the components of flood management systems (Sewnet, 2020).

Climate Change on Stormwater Drainage in Urban Areas

Climate change directly and indirectly affects the performance of the drainage network and causes the system to change. This is because climate change causes changes in hydrological components (Kumar, et al., 2022). Climate change directly and indirectly affects the performance of the drainage network and causes the system to change. This is because climate change causes changes in hydrological components. The economic, social, and ecological impacts of climate change affect the timing and quality of the rainfall regime. Changing rainfall intensity also has a high impact on infrastructure systems. This affects the safety of people and cities (Moore, Gulliver, Stack, & Simpson, 2016). Climate change involves many risks for urban areas. The most important of these risks are sea rise, coastal flooding, radical changes in precipitation regimes, drought, and heat stresses. Urban flood risk is a major problem for many industrialized countries. The calculations of climate change simulations indicate that rainfall intensity will increase by 60% by 2100, indicating that urban flood risks will increase significantly. Flood water management is a key component of climate change policies. These components include water conservation, health protection, and biodiversity. In addition, the methodology includes low low-impact development model and green infrastructure systems (Henstra, Thistlethwaite, & Vanhoore, 2020). The expansion of urban areas has led to a rapid increase in environmental problems. This has led to problems in traditional urban water management. There are serious problems with the capacity of basic pipe networks, wastewater management, and resilience to natural disasters. Stormwater management has been developed to solve these problems. Climate change disrupting the hydrological cycle has also triggered the development of stormwater management. Therefore, stormwater management with permeable pavements, green roofs, infiltration trenches, bio-retention cells, and vegetation swales has been developed (Yu, Xiao, Chang, Zhi , & Shen, 2022) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Stormwater Management Model Systems
(References: Global Designing Cities Initiative, 2024)

The use of low-impact development models for solving drainage problems caused by climate change and reducing flood risk with this method is an important development for urban areas. This method also improves the quality of urban water. It also improves adaptation to changing climate conditions (Pyke, et al., 2011).

Material and Methods

Study Area

The Çiğli district is bordered by Menemen to the north, Karşıyaka district to the east, and the Aegean Sea to the south and west. It covers a total surface area of 139 square kilometers. Families migrating from the Balkans first settled in this district in 1893. In the 1950s, the area saw changes with the development of informal housing, and following the administrative division in 1992, it became the district with the largest area. The elevation of the district center is between 1 and 1.5 meters above sea level. It boasts a 6 km long coastline along the Aegean Sea (Batı Plan, 2023) (Figure 3).

Figure 3. İzmir Çiğli District

İzmir Katip Çelebi University, which is the subject of the study, was established as 10 faculties, 3 institutes, and 1 college with the Law No. 6005 on the Law on the Organization of Higher Education Institutions and the Law on the Amendment of Certain Laws and Decree Laws published in the Official Gazette No. 27648 on 21.07.2010. It is located in Çiğli district (Figure 4).

İzmir Katip Çelebi University

Figure 4. İzmir Katip Çelebi University Location

Method

In this study, the initial task was to generate a digital elevation model (DEM). A DEM is a digital or 3-D representation of a terrain's surface, created using elevation data. This model provides a detailed depiction of the earth's surface, including natural and man-made features. The term digital elevation model (DEM) is often used to describe this representation, as it includes all objects on the surface, such as buildings and vegetation. Typically, DEMs are presented in raster format, which consists of a grid of cells, each representing a specific elevation (Balasubramanian, 2017).

As part of the drainage density analysis for the Çiğli district, the Alos Palsar Digital Elevation Model, which offers a resolution of 12.5 meters, is used. This high-resolution model was essential for accurately capturing the topography of the area. By using the Alos Palsar DEM, we were able to determine the elevation model of the Çiğli district. This model served as the foundation for further analysis, allowing us to assess the drainage patterns and identify potential areas of concern. The detailed elevation data provided by the DEM enabled a comprehensive examination of the terrain, facilitating a thorough understanding of the district's drainage characteristics. Watershed analysis was first performed to scale the drainage depth. Within the scope of this analysis, the land is divided into sub-catchments using a digital elevation model. Within the framework of hydrology analysis, fill-flow-accumulation and stream order calculations were made and a stream network was created on the basis of the study area. The sub-catchments associated with this were clarified. After basin polygons and stream networks are determined, water basins are identified. In-stream order analysis, flow paths, and degrees are determined by using the Strahler method. After this analysis is completed, grids of 1 square kilometer are created. After the intersection of these grids with the stream system, the length of the stream is calculated. After this calculation, interpolation analysis is performed, which helps to make the spatial distribution of drainage density by interpolation calculation. As a result of this analysis, drainage density regions are calculated (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Study Method

Results

As a result of all these analyzes, a drainage intensity map was created and a drainage classification was prepared for the entire sub-catchment within the borders of Çiğli district. The intensity level of each sub-catchment is shown in Figure 6. As a result of the analysis, the darker colored places were determined as places with high depth and the lighter blue places were determined as places with low depth. The characteristics of the low-density areas and the high density areas are different from each other. These differences are evident in infiltration rates, lower runoff rates and soil sediment transport rates. Areas with different spatial characteristics showed different drainage characteristics.

Figure 6. Drainage Density Map

In this context, İzmir Katip Çelebi University, located in Çiğli district, was identified as a site with high drainage intensity. It is a place with a high potential for water accumulation in cases of heavy rainfall. High or low drainage density directly affects the intervention methods to be implemented throughout the area as it varies according to the character of the area. Therefore, low-interaction development models can be applied depending on the character of the area.

Conclusion

In areas with high drainage intensity, project design and planning should be carried out with care. The rapid collection and runoff of rainwater in these areas can pose various challenges such as erosion, flood risk and soil stability. Here are the key considerations for project design and planning in such areas: Across the area, hydraulic and hydrology analysis will help to clarify the types of interventions where drainage intensity is identified. In this context, rainfall intensity analysis and runoff model analysis will be decisive in calculating flow velocity and depth. In addition, erosion and sediment control studies should be carried out throughout the area. Sediment collection locations, erosion protection methods, and natural vegetation cycle are important. Infrastructure design is important for any flooding situation. Drainage networks are created throughout the city with infrastructure design. Drainage ditches and drainage channels are important. The design of permeable surfaces throughout the area is important for areas with intensive drainage. Together with all these studies, risk analysis, and management are important for emergency planning.

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